

Point-to-multipoint Coherent Transceivers for Next-Generation Mobile Transport

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Abstract: Point-to-multipoint coherent transceivers can enable high-capacity and cost-effective bidirectional transmission for x-Haul networks. This contribution reviews the technology, requirements and potential to support next-generation mobile transport networks.

1. Introduction

Global forecasts are unanimous in identifying the key aspects that modern optical systems have to address to support next-generation mobile transport. They include (i) the pervasive deployment of Beyond 5G (B5G) and Internet of Things (IoT) devices [1]; (ii) the challenging increase in bandwidth demand [2]; (iii) the reduction in power consumption of the end-to-end solution [3]; (iv) the need for flexible bandwidth adaptation [4, 5]; and (v) the latency requirements [6].

Existing 4G/5G Radio Access Network (RAN) rely on a mix of optical and microwave transmission to send mobile transport traffic over distance. Optical transmission is typically implemented with legacy technology such as 10G/25G Intensity Modulation Direct-Detection (IM-DD), which is a cost-effective solution to satisfy the network requirements of currently deployed services [7]. Future B5G and 6G are envisioned to support higher capacities while lowering power consumption [8]. As an example, Fig. 1 illustrates the evolution of RAN connectivity for different scenarios. In this context, hardware and the scalability & configurability of software (e.g., enabling flexible bandwidth allocation) will play an important role in helping operators to plan, manage and control their networks more efficiently [4,5,9,10]. Moreover, the possibility to adopt pay-as-you-grow deployment strategies will help operators to deploy resources optimally, to simplify planning, and to mitigate the risk of overprovisioning [11].

Fig. 1: Evolution of connectivity solution for RAN. Radio Unit (RU), Distributed Unit (DU), Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI), Enhanced CPRI (eCPRI), Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM), Centralized RAN (CRAN).

Central to network evolution is the goal of reducing carbon emissions and unnecessary latency, e.g., introduced by unnecessary Opto-Electro-Optical (OEO) conversions. Approaches such as the one proposed in [11], which offer a better fit to support hub-and-spoke traffic in the optical domain by reducing the number of devices required, will increase the savings in cost and power consumption. Fully meshed topologies can further enhance the flexibility offered by CRAN and enhance advanced RAN coordination functions [12].

This contribution presents the requirements of next-generation mobile transport and describes coherent Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) transceivers as a possible way to meet them. We introduce two optical technologies that could support such systems: P2MP coherent transceivers enabled by Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM) and pluggable amplifiers. Finally, we present two relevant use cases: (i) flexible bandwidth allocation and Bidirectional (BiDi) transmission; and (ii) RAN architecture based on WDM horseshoe implementing a fully meshed interconnection pattern.

2. Requirements for 5G/6G mobile transport networks

Today’s most popular optical solutions for 5G radio use 25G pluggable transceivers, with 50G as the next step [13]. The enormous bandwidth that will be required by future 6G applications will further increase bandwidth requirements in the RAN transport [2]. In this context, coherent is gaining momentum on shorter distance applications and the market is following, as demonstrated by the success of “*open standards*” supported by a wide vendor base like “400G ZR” [14]. Technology adaptation from Data Center (DC) Point-to-Point (P2P) inter-connect to telecom carrier use-cases, where metro ring and regional meshed topologies are common, has generated new “*open standards*” like the 400G “Open ZR+” [15] Multi-Source Agreement (MSA). The typical metro ring topology is being considered for the connectivity needs of edge computing in telecom networks [16] and can be mapped similarly to the RAN use-case, provided that the cost for coherent technology will meet RAN requirements.

Coherent “*lite*” has consolidated as a trend towards cost/performance optimization for shorter reach. In the DC segment, the trend is motivated by DC-interconnect needs [17] (e.g., the 800G-LR activity at Optical Internetworking Forum (OIF)). With 1.6 Tb/s transmission on the radar, higher rates will push coherent technology further in the short distance domain. In telecom, the process has already produced optimized “*coherent lite*” solutions at 100G to cover the so-called metro-access edge [18].

Such considerations lead us to believe that “*coherent lite*”, including those based on DSCM to enable high capacity P2MP transmission, might play a fundamental role in future 6G RAN and RAN transport. For example, coherent P2MP significantly simplifies the network architecture by reducing the number of needed transceivers, leading to a considerable decrease in the total cost of ownership, and a significant increase in capacity and flexibility in the network design and management. Despite the fact that today’s coherent technology has been designed for metro and is too expensive for RAN, we believe the general cost pressure on coherent technology coming from the DC use-cases will generate “*coherent lite*” solutions at 400G and below, and could fit the RAN in the 2026 – 2030 timeframe.

This would not be the first time that metro technologies were adapted to varying cost/performance RAN sweet spots - today’s 10G/25G Dense WDM (DWDM) transceivers in use in optical Front-haul (FH) are a good example. In any case, adaptation to mobile transport implies addressing temperature and synchronization requirements, and single fibre operation would also be a desirable feature [11].

Fig. 2: Example of aggregation scenario using coherent P2MP enabled by DSCM. The figure shows a series of leaf nodes (e.g., B5G/6G antennas), transmitting at various rates: leaf #1-2 at 25G, leaf #3 at 75G, and leaf #N at 100G.

3. Enabling technologies

3.1. Digital subcarrier multiplexing enabling P2MP coherent transceivers

Fig. 2 shows the communication concept for high-speed coherent pluggable transceivers capable of supporting P2MP connections. These pluggables utilize Digital Signal Processing (DSP) to subdivide the transmission and reception of a given wavelength spectrum into a series of smaller-frequency channels called digital subcarriers. The digital subcarriers can be independently managed and assigned to different destinations, enabling direct low- to high-speed optical transceiver connectivity. In Fig. 2, we assume leaf node transceivers capable of transmitting up to 100G ($4 \times 25G$) at 4 GBaud using 16 Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (16-QAM) and dual polarization; while the hub node operates at the same conditions, but can use up to 16 digital subcarriers [11, 19] for a total of 400G ($16 \times 25G$). As the subcarriers

are generated in the digital domain, only one laser is needed.

High-speed connectivity, however, is not everything; modern architectures and traffic patterns in metro/access networks need to be supported in a robust yet flexible manner [4]. While the former is ensured by mature and proven communication techniques such as coherent transmission and DSP, the latter is enabled by the freedom allowed by DSCM. For example, when the 400G P2MP transceiver acts as a transmitter in a downstream scenario, transmitting flows from the hub site to leaf nodes, the multi-carrier signal is broadcast to multiple leaf nodes (e.g., antennas), each of which can extract a single subcarrier or a group thereof, according to the traffic characteristics. This allocation of resources at the transmitter opens the door to dynamic adjustments for subcarriers to better match the ebb and flow of traffic patterns during the day, as there are times when networks need to address more critical scenarios [5, 9]. By operating in this fashion, the hub node can utilize a single transceiver to communicate with up to 16 leaf nodes simultaneously, with each node receiving a single 25G subcarrier¹. For an upstream scenario, multiple single subcarriers or groups of them which may have different origins, are combined into a single multi-carrier signal. Given that subcarriers could have different levels of distortions (both linear and non-linear), the robustness and effectiveness of the DSP algorithms is a non-trivial aspect of the design of the P2MP transceiver [11].

Fig. 3: Flexible bandwidth allocation of digital subcarriers in a FH-like scenario using BiDi transmission.

3.2. Pluggable optical amplifiers

While optical amplifiers are tolerated at Central Office (CO) and hub sites, they are usually not allowed at RU and cell sites due to their large footprint, power consumption and cost. Compact optical amplifiers implemented in Pluggable Optical Line Systems (POLs), where wavelength combiners introduce a high insertion loss would be highly beneficial and allow the upgrade to higher bit-rates. Up to two amplifiers, for limited spectrum (e.g. 8 DWDM channels), or a single full C-band amplifier, can be fitted into the Quad Small Form Factor Pluggable Double Density (QSFP-DD) format. A POLs eliminates the need for a stand-alone line system and allows direct management from the host (switch, front-haul system), enabling plug-and-play configuration and removing the need for a separate optical management plane.

4. Relevant use cases for network architectures that support beyond 5G mobile transport

4.1. Flexible bandwidth allocation and BiDi transmission

Flexible bandwidth allocation refers to a scenario where the time-variant behavior of the traffic across a network is addressed by adapting the operating conditions of the transceivers. Fig. 3 illustrates a network with three sectors (business, entertainment, and residential areas). Here, as people carry out their daily or weekly activities, specific

¹This is possible by enabling communication between a low-speed module and a high-speed one.

traffic patterns will emerge: e.g., larger amounts of traffic in the late morning and early afternoon for the business sector during the working week, larger amounts of traffic in the early evenings and on weekends for the entertainment district, and larger amounts of traffic late at night for the residential areas. This ebb and flow of data can be approached on two different levels by leveraging a coherent P2MP transmission paradigm: software and hardware². For the former, Subcarriers (SCs) can be digitally enabled and disabled as needed to better match the requirements of the network. If a node in the network is observing traffic levels of 67 Gb/s, as shown in the business district during the day, instead of utilizing the whole bandwidth of a standard 100G transceiver, or the 4×25 Gb/s SCs of a P2MP transceiver, three SCs could be activated to address the traffic demands more efficiently at that point in time. Similarly, the entertainment district does not demand bandwidth during the day (0 SCs), while in the evening, perhaps because of sport events, it might require full capacity (4 SCs) as shown in Fig. 3.

Knowing that an optical signal has fewer SCs than the maximal nominal value, the hardware could save processing power by scaling down the complexity of the DSP and, accordingly, its calculations, at both the transmitter and receiver. There are consequences at the hardware level, since reducing or increasing the number of SCs has a direct impact in the operating conditions of lasers and amplifiers and can make a signal robust to filtering penalties and non-linearities. Therefore, by allocating resources dynamically, i.e., optimizing the software-hardware relations, coherent P2MP networks could provide advantages in terms of resource management, transmission performance, and power efficiency³. Furthermore, this use case supports, with an alternative optical physical layer implementation, the concept of a flexible gateway discussed in [4], where the re-provisioning of radio connections is foreseen to any Base-Band Unit (BBU) or Virtualized Distributed Unit (vDU). Such an architecture presents the following benefits: (i) it reduces Operational Expenditure (OPEX) by lowering the number of human interventions (e.g., truck-rolls); (ii) it improves the bandwidth utilization by providing the optimal bandwidth to all users; (iii) it helps operators in multi-year planning by using automation tools [21]; and finally (iv) it allows operators to roll out innovative technologies so that data-rate can be increased, while cost reduced.

Fig. 4: RAN architecture based on WDM horseshoe implementing a fully logical meshed interconnection. The scenario considers both duplex fiber and single fiber/ BiDi.

4.2. RAN architecture based on WDM horseshoe implementing a fully meshed interconnections

The trend for 6G is to move to a more user-centric Base-Bands (BBs) processing where a fully meshed connectivity between radios and BBs is established, allowing independent processes to be flexibly managed, exploiting optimization in the cloud. Such a decomposition, in fact, allows the creation of several fine-grained network functions autonomously executed in a cloud infrastructure. The physical layer proposed here, to provide a logical fully meshed interconnectivity between RUs and vDUs, is based on a WDM horseshoe/ring topology shown in Fig. 4. The fully meshed interconnectivity is logically built over the ring exploiting optical add/drop multiplexer integrated with POLS.

²Transmission can be realized with duplex and single fiber/BiDi.

³For example, an antenna could transmit overnight a lower data-rate and with a low order modulation formats to reduce the amount of consumed power [20].

Fig. 5: FH node implementation options.

This approach allows fiber resources savings, avoiding a full physical mesh interconnection. 100 – 400G coherent pluggable transceivers (either P2P or P2MP) provide the required capacity scaling expected by 6G.

The FH nodes can be implemented according to different options, as shown in Fig. 5. At the main site, a packet FH node [22] is deployed allowing for full flexibility. Coherent interfaces up to 400G can be used. At the remote site, according to different costs, real estate, and power consumption requirements three options are given: (i) a packed FH node, similar to the one implemented at the main site (Fig. 4a); (ii) a passive FH deployment, where coherent optics are directly plugged in the radio equipment (Fig. 4b). This solution, while removing the switch box, presents some challenges: thermal issues with direct use of high-speed DWDM optics in Remote Radio Unit (RRU)'s, and non-compatibility with today's Small Form-factor Pluggable (SFPx) pluggable practice of RRU's and tomorrow's co-packaged optics approach for RRUs; (iii) a FH node based on a "muxponder" unit, where subcarrier shuffling between the line optics and the very short reach client optics is exploited (Fig. 4c). Options 2 and 3 take advantage of the use of P2MP coherent pluggables based on the flexible allocation of subcarriers.

The optical infrastructure needs will be covered with the ultimate step of disaggregation. Today's simple P2P solutions [23] will be complemented over time by an increasing number of elementary functionalities like EDFAs, splitters, Optical Channel Monitors (OCMs), Optical Time-domain Reflectometers (OTDRs), in pluggable modules, which can be composed into full optical line systems tailored to the specific RAN transport scenarios. An example of POLS-based OADM, suitable for the proposed RAN architecture, is shown in Fig. 6: a dual pluggable EDFA followed by a colorless add/drop (splitters) provides the required amplification and re-configurability functions. The filtering is guaranteed by the coherent demultiplexing provided by the Local Oscillator (LO) and the tunability of the coherent transceiver allows for routing flexibility to perform, for example, load balancing between the servers instantiating the vDUs.

Fig. 6: Optical Add and Drop Multiplexers (OADM) based on simple, transparent, non-selective splitters and pluggable Erbium Doped Fiber Amplifiers (EDFAs).

5. Conclusions

We presented an overview of how point-to-multipoint coherent transceivers can help in the deployment of next-generation mobile transport networks. The requirements for telecommunication systems to support beyond 5G/6G (demand for high capacity, i.e., $\geq 400\text{G}$, enhanced flexibility in bandwidth allocation and severe constraints on power consumption and latency) can all be tackled through the proposed solution, utilizing digital subcarrier multiplexing, which offers operators the essential flexibility in both hardware and software, enabling high-capacity operations and reducing latency by eliminating unnecessary Opto-Electro-Optical conversions. In this respect, a ring-based fronthaul architecture has been presented implementing a logical full mesh between Distributed Units and Radio Units: Point-to-Multipoint coherent transceivers provide a sub-wavelength granularity that offers a lean alternative to the use of additional packet switches equipment.

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